

Methods for optimizing labor resource management in an enterprise based on a logistical approach

Bashar Shirinov

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Business Economics and Management, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor, Baku, Azerbaijan ORCID 0000-0003-4872-4035 revan622@mail.ru

Nigar Aliyeva

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Business Economics and Management, Doctor of Philosophy in Economics, Senior Lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan, ORCID 0000-0001-5845-8565, nigar24-87@mail.ru

Namig Kazimov

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Business Economics and Management, Senior Lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan, ORCID 0000-0002-4580-8404, eko_dent@mail.ru

Aynur Gurbanova

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Industrial Organization and Management, lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan, ORCID: 0000-0003-0878-9889, aynur.qurbanova.76@mail.ru

Hasanova Gunel

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Industrial Organization and Management, lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan, ORCID 0000-0002-86200-163 gunel_ns@mail.ru

Matanat Aliyeva

Azerbaijan University of Architecture and Construction, Department of Business Economics and Management, Senior Lecturer, Baku, Azerbaijan, ORCID 0000-0002-3608-4352, metanet.aliyeva.0067@mail.ru

ABSTRACT:

This article examines the importance of the logistic approach in optimizing labor resource management in terms of optimal cost savings, rational dismissal and redistribution of employees, which are a necessary condition for the development and efficiency of production in many state and private enterprises, industries, and regions.

The work examines the solution of these problems related to the development of a system for providing various sectors of the economy with labor resources based on the logistic approach. The solution to this problem lies in the field of economic and mathematical methods of linear programming, where, for ease of understanding, the problem of the optimal plan for distributing labor resources from their training centers to employment centers with minimal costs is considered.

The main methods used to solve scientific and practical problems in logistics include system analysis, operations research, and forecasting. These methods allow predicting material flows, creating integrated systems for controlling and monitoring their movement, developing logistics service systems, optimizing inventory, and solving a number of other problems. The article analyzes the possibilities of solving these problems related to the development of a system for providing various sectors of the economy with labor resources based on a logistics approach.

Keywords: logistics approach; enterprise; models; principles; labor resources; competition; human resources; methods; optimization; evaluation method.

I. INTRODUCTION

The modern economy is characterized by dynamic development. The general expansion of economic development is accompanied by constant changes in the internal structure of the economy. In these conditions, labor becomes an active factor of production. The increasing requirements for efficient labor management are primarily due to the acceleration of scientific and technological progress. The increasing complexity of production, the increasing importance of such components as training, retraining, continuous training, monitoring and management,

initial and redistribution of personnel, as well as the need to increase labor efficiency by minimizing personnel costs, necessitate consideration of the problem of logistical management of labor flows.

There is an urgent need for methods of managing labor resources and increasing their competitiveness, as well as for the transition of the economy to the path of intensive development. In many state and private enterprises, industries, regions, there is an urgent need for optimal cost savings, rational dismissal and redistribution of workers, which are a necessary condition for the development of production and increasing efficiency.

From the point of view of personnel supply, logistical management of labor flows can be considered as strategic management covering the formation, distribution and use of labor resources at the national, regional and industry levels. It is aimed at reducing costs associated with the formation, initial and subsequent distribution of labor and rationalizing their use at both the micro and macro levels, including continuous training. Labor flows are dual in nature: a surplus of labor results in the creation of "short-term" labor reserves; labor shortages result in a shortage of specialists, either in certain professions or in certain areas or industries. Both situations lead to increasing financial losses in future periods.

II. Analysis of recent researches and publications

The main problem facing organizations today is high staff turnover, the main reason for which is the lack of social HR management technologies such as recruitment, adaptation, development and motivation in the general management system.

Stabilization is a stable team environment. Today, successful staff development contributes to the creation of a more skilled and highly motivated workforce to achieve the organization's goals.

It should be borne in mind that the staff composition has a great impact on the efficiency of the enterprise. Therefore, the issue of planning, development and retention of the staff composition is becoming increasingly relevant for managers at all levels.

The staff of an enterprise is a set of employees of various professional and skill groups hired by the organization and included in its payroll [1].

The main features of the staff composition of an enterprise are [2]:

1. The presence of labor relations formalized by an employment contract with the employer.
2. The presence of certain qualitative characteristics (profession, specialty, qualification, competence, etc.) that determine the duties of the employee and their activities at a specific workplace.
3. Directing the activities of personnel in accordance with the established goals and creating conditions for their effective implementation.

One of the characteristics of personnel is the professional and qualification structure of personnel. This concept includes three closely related but independent aspects [2]:

1. Professional structure of personnel.
2. Qualification structure of personnel.
3. Content of qualification requirements.

The professional structure of personnel refers to the proportion of employees representing different professional groups.

The qualification structure refers to the proportion of employees with different qualification levels.

The content of qualification requirements is a set of skills, experience and knowledge necessary to perform work. The nature of the technology used is directly related to the qualification requirements of the employee performing labor activities in a specific workplace [3].

Human resources (HR) are a set of employees of various professional and skill groups and staff within the organization. In connection with the constant development of technology, technical equipment, the emergence of new types of goods and services, changes in the social structure of society and economic restructuring, the personnel structure of the organization is subject to constant changes in professional and skill levels. Therefore, at any time the structure of employees in the main professional and skill groups is very variable.

HR development is a key component of the HR system, the main components of which are: planning of personnel needs; recruitment and selection; personnel development; placement and assessment of personnel.

The modern economy dictates new rules of the game. Organizations that operate effectively in the market establish new relationships with employees. In conditions of constantly accelerating changes, a new type of organizational contract is emerging, reminiscent of a commercial partnership.

The employee and the employer agree to cooperate only as long as it is beneficial for both parties. This, of course, requires full commitment from both the employee and the organization. Changes are taking place in relations between people. Market contracts have replaced verbal agreements.

An interesting method for stabilizing personnel is the use of HR logistics. HR logistics is understood as a branch of logistics that studies the optimization of the flow of labor resources within the organization and within the industry as a whole [4].

According to scientists, the main goal of HR logistics is formed based on the general logistical rule of the “seven H”: to provide the company with the necessary personnel with the appropriate qualifications required by the company at the right time (taking into account current and future human resource needs), in the right quantity and in the right place (for specific tasks).

HR logistics answers the following questions:

- does the enterprise need personnel and if so, what kind?
- is there a need to transfer employees to other departments of the company?
- which employees should be promoted or demoted?
- will moving up or down the ladder or to another department of the company motivate the employee?
- which employees should be fired to make way for other employees?
- how should vacant positions be treated?

Modern organizations face many problems that could be avoided if they were staffed with people.

A logistician is a specialist who plans, controls and manages the movement of inventory, as well as organizes the movement of goods and services from suppliers to consumers.

Such specialists are extremely important and indispensable for modern companies focused on rapid development. A person engaged in logistics must have many important qualities in order to achieve effective results. The most important of these qualities are: the ability to focus on the most important issues, moving away from secondary complexities; constant improvement of oneself and one's work; commitment to development.

Among the qualities required of a logistics specialist, it is important to highlight the personal qualities necessary for the job and the professional skills that allow a person to be the most effective and useful for the organization.

The professional and personal qualities of a logistics specialist include:

- reliable interlocutors and direct interaction with suppliers and customers, requiring experience;
- preparation of documents (primary documentation, its subsequent systematization and submission to regulatory authorities);
- hard work is one of the most important qualities for anyone who wants to succeed;
- an inquisitive mind and observation are qualities necessary for finding new ideas in everyday work;
- the ability to form and place orders;
- planning purchases;
- interaction with customs authorities;
- coordination of warehouse services;
- development of cargo delivery routes;
- knowledge of various types of transport;
- knowledge of procurement, warehousing and distribution logistics;
- knowledge of modern technologies and software required for work;
- language skills. Ambition is a necessary quality that helps to overcome any obstacles on the path to success;
- analytical thinking. This allows you to assess the chances of success of any idea, analyze past mistakes and make appropriate adjustments;
- the ability to make unconventional decisions;
- creativity. This feature implies a creative approach, unconventional thinking and the absence of boundaries or restrictions;
- systems thinking – the ability to predict how actions and decisions will affect a system of interacting processes;
- communication skills are important, as the logistics specialist must be able to establish relationships with suppliers, contractors, government agencies, etc.

Therefore, it can be said that a logistics specialist is responsible for practically the entire life cycle of manufactured products, including production, storage, distribution and delivery. They organize and control the transportation of goods and cargo, and therefore must have the professional skills, knowledge and personal qualities necessary for working in the logistics field.

HR logistics should ensure that existing company jobs, which impose specific requirements on employees (personal qualities and qualifications), are adapted to employees with different skills, professional training and qualifications. This adaptation occurs as a result of constant changes in the requirements of employees, as well as in the conditions and content of their work. Therefore, the formation of the company's workforce flow requires a continuous selection of the most effective options, taking into account all conditions and factors. In order to effectively implement this selection, it is necessary to clearly understand the company's HR goals.

Thus, investments in human resources and talent development based on the logistics approach become one of the most important factors of corporate competitiveness. HR logistics should be flexible and dynamic, adapting to changes that occur as the organization develops. However, it is also important to remember that it should also have stable priorities. This is very important when working with people, since many of the expectations of employees are based on stable relationships with the organization.

Providing various sectors of the economy with labor resources based on the logistics approach involves solving the following strategic and tactical tasks (table .1).

Table .1

Strategic and tactical tasks of providing economic sectors with labor resources based on the logistics approach

Strategic goals	Tactical tasks
timely training of specialists needed by enterprises and regions	optimization of the structure of labor resources in the labor market
recruitment of specialists at optimal costs	
insurance of enterprises and trained specialists against various unforeseen situations	optimization of the spatial distribution of labor resources
consolidation of labor resources	
formation of levels of logistics services (strategies for providing industries with labor resources, action plans, regulatory and legal framework, field control system, a certain complex of services accompanying the delivery of labor resources to enterprises in need of them), educational services	determination of the degree of concentration and centralization of enterprises.
development of integration and coordination of interaction between employment services and recruitment agencies of different regions	

Note: The table was compiled by the author.

The main characteristics of the labor flow include: type, scale, level of qualification, frequency of movement, trajectory of movement, number of participants, method of movement, characteristics of the career space, time orientation, reason for movement, generational level of social position, connection with the previous place of work, source of movement, demographic components of the flow, results of the flow movement, intensity (number) of the flow in certain periods. To regulate the flow of labor in any direction, the entire arsenal of socio-economic and organizational-administrative measures should be used. In this case, economic levers are the most important and most effective.

The solution of these problems related to the development of a system for providing various sectors of the economy with labor resources based on a logistics approach will allow:

- to make the most efficient use of the resources of labor resources available in the country;
- rationally conduct professional training of labor resources (with a focus on the end consumer (requirements of enterprises));
- reduce the payback period for expenses related to vocational training;
- effectively use vocational training institutions, employment services and recruitment agencies, creating professional agencies by industry affiliation providing logistics services based on the following stages:
 - segmentation of the consumer market, i.e. division into specific groups of consumers for each of which labor resources are formed in accordance with the characteristics of enterprises;
 - determination of a list of professions that are more important for enterprises;
 - ranking (ordering) of professions included in the compiled list by their importance for enterprises, focusing on the most important professions;
 - formation of standards for training professional personnel for enterprises in consumer market segments;
 - evaluation of logistics services by establishing a link between the level of service, the cost of services provided, increased productivity and the competitiveness of end consumers (enterprises) of the service;
 - create feedback with enterprises to ensure that logistics services meet the needs of enterprises;
 - professional training of labor resources, search for jobs and eliminate ineffective financial losses associated with the release;
 - increase the maximum income and labor productivity of a trained specialist;
 - reduce the unemployment rate of the labor force, as well as the unemployment rate among young people.

Thus, one of the central goals of state policy in the field of providing economic sectors with labor resources can be achieved through the development of a system of high-quality and efficient formation, distribution and use of labor resources based on a material and technical approach.

Various modeling methods are widely used in logistics, that is, logistics systems and processes are studied by building and studying their models. A logistics model is defined as any abstract or material description of a logistics process or a logistics system used as a proxy.

The following models of a logistics system are distinguished.

According to the degree of completeness of similarity to the modeled objects and processes, all models are divided into isomorphic and homomorphic.

Isomorphic models are models that incorporate virtually all the properties of an object or phenomenon that can replace it. If such a model can be created, the behavior of the object can be accurately predicted. To create such models, significant resources are required; they can be built for relatively simple systems.

Homomorphic models are based on the imperfect similarity of the model with the object under study. Some aspects of the real object are not modeled at all. This simplifies the construction of the model and the interpretation of research results. Such models are more often used in the study of various systems, phenomena and processes. However, in some cases their reliability is very high, but the results obtained with them are probabilistic in nature.

Homomorphic models are divided into material and abstract models according to their significance.

Material models reflect the main spatial, physical, dynamic and functional characteristics of the object under study. This category includes, in particular, scale models of manufacturing plants and wholesale trade organizations that help solve the problems of optimal equipment placement and cargo flow management.

Abstract modeling is often the only modeling approach in logistics. It is divided into symbolic and mathematical models.

Symbolic models include linguistic and sign models.

Mathematical modeling is the process of establishing a correspondence between a given real-world object and a specific mathematical object, called a mathematical model. Two types of mathematical modeling are widely used in logistics: analytical and simulation.

Analytical modeling is a mathematical technique that allows you to find exact solutions for studying logistics systems. Analytical modeling is carried out in 3 stages (table 2).

Table 2
Analytical modeling stages

Stages	Analytical modeling
Stage I	Mathematical laws are formulated that link the components of the logistics system. These laws are written as functional relationships.
Stage II	Equations are solved and theoretical results are given.
Stage III	Theoretical results are compared with the actual values of the studied parameters or with real objects. The adequacy of the model is determined.

Note: The table is compiled by the author.

A more complete study of the system's performance can be carried out when explicit relationships are known that link the desired properties with the initial conditions, parameters and variables of the system. However, in practice, such relationships can only be obtained for relatively simple systems. To eliminate these dependencies, the initial model must be simplified.

The advantages of analytical modeling include greater generalization power and reusability.

Logistics systems operate in an uncertain external environment. In addition to uncertainty, this environment is also characterized by dynamism: many enterprises change their performance indicators quite often. In addition, material flow management must take into account factors, many of which are random. Under these conditions, the creation of an analytical model that establishes quantitative relationships between various components of logistics processes can be either impossible or very expensive.

In simulation modeling, the regularities that determine the nature of quantitative relationships within logistics processes remain unknown. During modeling, only the conditions of the input processes change, and depending on them, the results obtained at the output of the simulation model. The model itself is, so to speak, a "black box" with unknown processes inside.

Simulation modeling includes 2 main processes: I is the construction of a model of the real system, II is the construction of experiments on this model and obtaining results.

The following goals can be pursued:

- 1) understanding the behavior of the logistics system;
- 2) choosing a strategy that will ensure the most efficient operation of the logistics system.

Simulation modeling is usually carried out using computers.

The main conditions under which it is recommended to use simulation modeling are:

- 1) there are no complete mathematical methods for solving this problem;

2) analytical methods exist, but the procedures are so difficult and laborious that simulation modeling provides a simpler way to solve the problem;

3) analytical solutions exist, but their implementation is impossible due to insufficient training of the available personnel.

Thus, the main advantage of simulation modeling is that it can be used to solve more complex problems. Simulation models allow us to easily consider random effects and other factors that create difficulties in analytical research.

Simulation modeling repeats the operation of the system over time. The elementary events that make up the process are simulated, preserving their logical structure and time sequence.

Simulation modeling has some disadvantages. The main ones are as follows:

1. Research using this method is expensive. The reasons for this are:

- highly qualified specialists are required to build the model and conduct experiments on it;
- models are developed for critical conditions and, as a rule, are not repeated.

2. The risk of false imitation is high. Processes in logistics systems are probabilistic in nature and can only be modeled on the basis of certain assumptions

The decisive factor in the success of any enterprise is the efficient use of resources and opportunities, as well as the ability to quickly respond to changes in the competitive environment. In dynamic development, the lack of qualified personnel can be a major obstacle to the competitiveness and innovative development of the enterprise.

Human resources are especially important in this context. In modern market conditions, the development of the personnel potential of an enterprise is one of its main competitive advantages and an important condition for achieving and maintaining a stable or leading market position.

Human resources are a factor in the development of modern society, national wealth and quality of life depend on them. The category of "human resource potential" refers to the collective worker not only as a participant in production, but also as an integral part and driving force of all stages of the reproduction process, as a "carrier" of social needs, performing the function of goal-setting, objectively creating and subjectively determining the strategic and tactical goals of economic development. However, its scale cannot be reliably measured, since the components of the potential are the professional qualifications of employees, their scope and novelty cannot be determined.

Formulation of the objectives of the article. The purpose of the study is to develop and substantiate methodological approaches for methods of optimizing labor resource management at the enterprise based on a logistical approach.

III. STATEMENT OF THE MAIN MATERIAL OF THE STUDY.

Human resource management based on the principles of logistics is currently a promising method for increasing the efficiency of the organization, since the movement of personnel is impossible without systematization. By applying the principles of logistics and technologies based on them, it is possible to effectively manage the flow of human resources.

In organizational management, logistics is viewed as the strategic management of material flows to ensure that the enterprise is provided with everything necessary for the production of goods or the provision of services. Logistics aims to minimize costs within the enterprise and regulate the production process, both for one enterprise and for several enterprises, as well as the accompanying service and sales processes.

The basic principles of logistics can be applied to the personnel management system in an organization, for example: the required product is the required personnel; the required quality is the required qualifications and required professional skills; a sufficient number of employees is the required number; in the right place at a given workplace; at a given estimated time; with minimal costs [5].

These logistics principles can quite clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of the human resources management system and, accordingly, its ability to influence the functioning of the economic system as a whole.

At the current stage of the country's economic development, logistics is one of the most rapidly developing areas. Logistics activities are integrated and extend from the moment the need for a product or service arises to the moment the need is satisfied.

The main problems facing the development of logistics include: irrationally developing systems for the distribution of goods and services; underdeveloped communication and warehousing systems; the transport system is a legacy of the Soviet Union; outdated production of containers and packaging; insufficient qualified personnel.

The influx of new young specialists into logistics is very small, since this profession is relatively new in our country. Relatively few higher education institutions train specialists in this field. Therefore, people from related professions, such as economists, managers and marketers, who find themselves in logistics or supply chains during the development of the organization, work in this area.

One of the solutions to this problem is to conduct internships between universities and transport companies, followed by employment contracts. This is convenient for potential employers, as it gives them the opportunity to observe students at work in potential workplaces. It is also possible to conduct an initial selection of student candidates who already know their skills and knowledge in their professional field.

If the company does not have personnel with logistics education, then it is possible to provide advanced training in this area to existing employees.

However, theoretical knowledge is not the key to success. A simple example of this is the ABC method. Using this method, all objects are divided into three groups [9]:

A – 20% of valuable objects, accounting for 80% of all results;

B – 30% of objects, accounting for 15% of results;

C – 50% of objects, only 5% of the results.

This allows the company to focus all its efforts on a small group of important objects that affect the final result and, accordingly, structure the logistics of purchasing, inventory management and sales [3].

To solve logistics problems, the following algorithm can be used:

1. Study and characterize the system (a systematic approach to the object is assumed);
2. Identify problems in the system;
3. Set goals and objectives for solving the problem;
4. Select the right tools;
5. Apply the existing method, use several methods together or create a new one;
6. Determine the intermediate result;
7. Adjust the effect to improve the result.

It should be noted that there is no universal method for solving logistics problems; each enterprise develops a unique approach to solving problems within a specific enterprise.

Thus, the training of logistics personnel is an important problem. It is important to quickly integrate the logistics mindset into the work practices of top and middle managers, personnel in various enterprises and others. Intensive training in logistics, retraining and advanced training in this area are important for middle and top managers.

As can be seen, the scope of HR logistics is quite wide and demonstrates its effectiveness in HR management for any company, especially large ones. The need for HR logistics has become especially urgent in the modern market economy. Competition, which is the main feature of the market economy, forces any organization to strive for the most efficient use of its labor resources, HR logistics contributes to the full commitment of employees and the intensive development of their potential, thereby increasing the competitiveness of the organization. The effectiveness of HR logistics for the organization and its employees (table .3) is reflected in.

Table 3
The effectiveness of HR logistics for the organization and its personnel

For the organization	For employees
increased competitiveness in the market	intensive personnel development
maximum use of labor resources	career growth
improved corporate image	high level of motivation
using internal candidate search methods	effective personnel interaction between structural units (departments)
reducing organizational costs	strengthening of horizontal informal relations between employees
creating a unified HR environment	promotes employee retention within the corporation, creates healthy rotation opportunities, giving a chance to promising specialists

Note: The table was compiled by the author.

HR logistics should be directly based on the mission of the organization, since it is aimed at both operational and strategic management. This is especially relevant when making decisions about training certain employees or their release. Personnel assessment is important to ensure that HR logistics functions are performed with maximum efficiency.

Personnel assessment is a tool for assessing the competencies and performance of employees for personnel logistics purposes, namely: selecting and placing personnel; determining a reasonable salary level; identifying training needs; managing the talent pool; eliminating the company's crisis.

Assessment is divided into competency-based and activity-based assessments. Each performance assessment method must be reliable. Reliability means that repeated measurements give the same results as the previous one [9].

Of course, personnel assessment should be objective, but it is necessary to take into account the influence of subjective factors that affect performance: relationships with colleagues, management, and the organization's management style.

Assessment methods may vary depending on the size of the company, the number of employees, and the availability of funds.

Small firms with an authoritarian management style usually use subjective personnel assessment methods that do not require significant effort or financial investment. The most common selection method in small companies is an unstructured interview with the director, which, while demonstrating whether a person is suitable for his company, does not so much assess his actual skills. For example, a director may be satisfied with an average professional, but he is obedient, hardworking, and undemanding. This approach to assessment is widespread in small organizations. While retaining the final decision, managers may use other assessment methods, such as tests, "just to check the box." The use of more complex methods, especially in expensive organizations, is not cost-effective, so hiring outside experts for assessment, convening a certification committee, and especially conducting an assessment are rare. This happens when the company's activities are inextricably linked with the competence of its employees, proper staffing, and high profitability.

When it is necessary to assess a large number of employees, large companies use cheap and fast methods such as testing and paired comparisons. In addition, in the modern world, when organizations have a developed network of branches or subsidiaries in different cities and even countries, the issue of remote (virtual) assessment of employees arises. Naturally, the main method of assessing virtual personnel is testing. It can take various forms, from sending a text file with a test to the employee's e-mail, to using specialized online services, to information systems specially designed for remote testing of employees. The larger the company and the more resources it has, the more complex the method used. Online testing can be used in both medium and small organizations. There are specialized online services for online testing purposes.

If it is necessary to assess a small group of people within a large organization for the subsequent application of HR logistics methods, the following methods are used: case study methodology; workplace monitoring; certification; 360 degrees; competency-based interview; assessment center.

In large organizations, it is advisable to create an internal assessment center either as a separate department or as part of the personnel department.

Medium-sized companies can use any assessment method, depending on the number of employees to be assessed, financial capabilities and the level of development of the branch network.

In HR logistics, a comprehensive approach to personnel assessment is preferred. "The comprehensive approach includes the following main characteristics: professional behavior, personal initiative, quality of performance of functional duties, commitment to the development of professional and personal qualities" [8].

The best assessment method in human resources logistics is the assessment center - a comprehensive personnel assessment method based on the use of complementary methods, aimed at assessing the actual qualities of employees, their psychological and professional characteristics, their compliance with job requirements and determining the potential of specialists [2]. Subjects participate in business games under expert supervision, pass tests and interviews. This method most fully identifies the main employee qualities. In addition, this method can increase employee motivation and productivity by exposing employees to new, unfamiliar conditions, promoting team building and disrupting the daily routine.

Assessment centers can solve certain HR logistics problems with an accuracy of 87%: selecting the best candidate for a vacant position; identifying the potential of the candidate-employee; developing the talent pool; developing individual development programs and corporate personnel training programs.

Assessment centers use professional or management models to assess managers or specialists, as well as a corporate model that evaluates each employee based on a single set of competencies, taking into account the hierarchy. An assessment center can be successfully used to assess a small number of individuals, such as middle or senior managers in a medium or large organization, or a large part or all of a small, high-profit organization. Typically, a group consists of 6-12 people. An assessment center is usually carried out as follows: first, group tasks, including discussions, examples, role-playing, as well as tests and other written tasks under the supervision of the assessors, are carried out, then each employee is interviewed. An assessment center usually takes 1-3 days.

The HR specialist receives a comprehensive expert report on each employee assessed, which is then used to inform the subsequent logistical approach. However, this method significantly increases personnel costs, making it unacceptable for organizations with low profitability or requiring the assessment of a large number of employees.

Before using an assessment center, it is important to consider whether the future benefits of the assessment outweigh the costs. Moreover, it is now possible to complete the assessment center using a remote service.

Assessment methods such as competency-based interviews, case studies, 360-degree assessments, expert systems, and paired comparisons are suitable for HR logistics purposes.

Expert systems can also be involved in the HR logistics process. These systems allow for the assessment of personnel as a first step using tests (including psychological ones).

Then, based on the results of the assessment, they make recommendations for personnel placement, identify training needs, demonstrate parameters such as job suitability, learning ability, motivation, predict professional success, and most importantly, allow all these processes to be carried out centrally and quickly.

IV. CONCLUSION

Labor logistics of the enterprise is a branch of logistics that studies the optimization of labor resource flows within enterprises and the industry as a whole. Labor logistics of the enterprise has four main areas, including optimization of input, output and internal flows related to management goals.

The program for applying the logistics system approach to labor resource management at the enterprise includes a certain sequence of activities to assess the organization of the personnel management system, assess the labor potential of the enterprise, and assess the state of corporate culture at the enterprise and the socio-psychological climate of the team.

The logistics system approach to labor resource management is the optimization of components of labor logistics processes for each block (input flows, internal flows and output flows) in the form of a functional model in the relationship between quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The labor resource management system of the enterprise includes: optimization of input, internal and output flows by elements, taking into account the relationship between qualitative and quantitative aspects; indicators of the effectiveness of labor potential management; assessment of the labor potential of the enterprise's employees as a whole.

Indicators of the economic efficiency of labor resources management should include two subsystems - indicators of the economic efficiency of labor resources management and indicators of the economic efficiency of the enterprise due to the effective management of labor resources.

In the system of indicators of the efficiency of labor resources management, the general indicator characterizing the economic efficiency of the enterprise is the labor productivity indicator characterizing the profitability of production per employee.

Thus, HR logistics is a tool for effective management of a modern organization. HR logistics contributes to the full commitment of employees and the intensive development of their potential, thereby increasing the competitiveness of the organization.

In addition, HR logistics allows organizations to save material and time costs associated with personnel by simplifying HR management. One of the main tools in HR logistics is personnel assessment. The best assessment methods in HR logistics include assessment centers, online tests on specialized Internet servers, and expert systems.

REFERENCES

- 1.Chala TG, Hrynychak NA (2019) Statistical assessment and forecasting of logistics services Market development in Ukraine. *Mod Eng Innov Technol* (13)/Part 2:99–106
- 2.. Ganushchak, T.(2017) Dynamics of development of financial safety of the enterprise as a complex economic security of the state.*Baltic journal of economic studies*, № 3(4), - pp. 32-37 [Google Scholar]. [Cross Ref].
3. Imanov T.I. (2005) *Fundamentals of logistics*, vol. I, Education, Baku.
4. Imanov T.I. (2010) *Fundamentals of logistics*, vol. II., Education, Baku.
5. Yesenkin B.S., Krylova M.D. *Logistics in the book business*. Moscow, Moscow State University of Printing Arts, 2002. 335 p.
6. Panasenko E.V. (2011) *Logistics: Personnel, Technologies, Practice*, Moscow: INFRA, Engineering.
- 7.Shatt D.G. (2008.) *Goods Flow Management: A Guide to Optimizing the Logistics of Chepochek*. Moscow: Grevtsova.
8. Sekerin V.D. (2015) *Logistics*, Moscow: KNORUS.
- 9.Shirinov B. (2021) The role of logistic analysis methods in the Enterprise Resource Management System. *Economy and State*, pp. 83–86.
- 10.Shirinov Bashar Habib oglu, Velizade Fidan, Mazahir, and Huseynov Jamil Zaur oglu (2024). Factors affecting the efficiency of labor productivity of the enterprise *Economy and Region*, No. 3 (94).
- 11.Shynkar, S., Gontar, Z., Dubyna, M., Nasypaiko, D. and Fleychuk, M. Assessment of the economic security of enterprises: theoretical and methodological aspects. // - *Business: Theory and Practice*, - 2020, No. 21(1), - pp. 261-271 [Google Scholar], [Cross Ref].
12. Vusal Gasimli, Masuma Talibova, Gunay Guliyeva, Ayaz Museyibov, Fuad Mirzayev, Aykhan Gadashov, Gulnara Ahmadova (2023) *Digital Economy: textbook*. Baku.